

A THREE-DIMENSIONAL DAMAGE MODEL FOR TRANSVERSELY ISOTROPIC COMPOSITES IN THE FRAMEWORK OF FINITE STRAIN

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ABSTRACT

Organic sheets are layered weave-reinforced composites. A main issue in modeling these kind of materials is the incomplete set of test data due to deformation modes not accessible through experiments. To overcome this problem, a virtual material characterization framework is set up based on so-called representative volume elements. The work at hand introduces a three-dimensional constitutive model for the prediction of damage onset and growth in unidirectional reinforced plastics, corresponding to the impregnated rovings in the aforementioned weaves. Taking into account large deformations, stress-based failure criteria and damage evolution laws are introduced. The entire constitutive response is implemented into an Abaqus user material routine. Numerical use cases demonstrate the characteristics of the material response for different loading scenarios.

1 MOTIVATION

An increasing number of composite materials consist of woven reinforcement structures impregnated by a polymeric matrix material. The present work examines the material group of organic sheets as an example for such composites. These are heterogeneous, layered structures, where each layer is built up by two planar interwoven sets of rovings impregnated by thermoplastic matrix. Rovings by themselves are composites of matrix and unidirectional (UD) arranged fibers. Figure 1 shows the microstructure of a weave-reinforced material at different length scales, where three relevant scales are identified:

1. Pure thermoplastic matrix (Figure 1(a))
2. UD fiber reinforced composite (Figure 1(b)): The combination of thermoplastic matrix and parallel fibers
3. Fiber weave-reinforced composite (Figure 1(c)): Interwoven rovings (UD structures) with matrix nestings

Figure 1: Top-down microstructure analysis for a glass fiber weave-reinforced structural part: (a) Pure thermoplastic matrix, (b) Unidirectional fiber reinforced composite, (c) Fiber weave-reinforced composite (combination of (a) and (b))

Following this picture, a multiscale approach can be established, allowing the description of the macroscopic part behavior, e.g. deformation and damage evolution. Hereby, mechanisms taking place on the different, relevant length scales can be transported to the macroscopic component scale. To overcome the shortcoming of incomplete experimental data due to the inability to characterize all possible deformation modes experimentally, the above-mentioned strategy helps to virtually characterize the material response in a computational manner. By simulating all intermediate scales, the material behavior of weave-reinforced thermoplastics becomes predictable. In the composite under focus, a thermoplastic polypropylene matrix represents the lowest scale that has to be modeled throughout the subsequent micro and meso models (unidirectional and woven).

Based on realistic geometries obtained from optical measurement techniques, representative volume elements (RVEs) for both microstructures are created. Exemplary realizations of such RVEs are shown in Figure 2. Carefully note that information from lower scales (e.g. UD) are subsequently used in higher scales (roving in weave) in the form of effective, homogenized material models. On the basis of FE calculations in combination with computational homogenization techniques and the development of adequate effective material models for transversely isotropic unidirectional (for the roving) and monoclinic woven glass fiber reinforced thermoplastics (for a woven layer), a scale transition can be realized. For further information on multiscale methods, the interested reader is referred to the works of Fish [7], Suquet [21], Guedes et al. [8], Terada et al. [22] and Miehe et al. [13], among others.

Figure 2: Illustration of microstructures for (a) a statistical representative UD reinforced composite consisting of 497 fibers (Volume fraction: $v_f=62.5\%$, edge length: $L_e=250\mu\text{m}$, fiber diameter: $d=10\mu\text{m}$) and (b) a twill weave unit cell layer (matrix domain is hidden)

The present work introduces a full three-dimensional continuum damage model for impregnated rovings, representing parallel fiber arrangement embedded in a thermoplastic matrix. On the macroscopic level, the woven structure experiences large deformations, especially rotations, which must be accounted for on the mesoscopic scale. To this end, a thermodynamically consistent constitutive model for transversely isotropic materials is derived in the finite strain setting with the capability of predicting damage onset and evolution. The model is implemented into the implicit finite element code Abaqus by using the material subroutine UMAT.

2 FINITE STRAIN DAMAGE MODEL FOR UD REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

2.1 Ground-state elasticity

Assuming initially transversal isotropic material behavior, an elastic constitutive formulation for large strain deformations is derived. The mentioned symmetry class requires one principal symmetry axis forming the normal of the transversely isotropic plane. For materials with unidirectional, aligned continuous fiber reinforcements (UD) this vector coincides with the fiber direction. In the reference configuration \mathbf{B}_0 this direction can be described by a normalized vector $\mathbf{A} = A_i \mathbf{e}_i$ with $|\mathbf{A}| = 1$. Due to the deformation it transforms to its counterpart in the current configuration \mathbf{B}_t , $\mathbf{a} = a_i \mathbf{e}_i$, by the tangent map with the deformation gradient \mathbf{F} (cf. Figure 3)

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{A}. \quad (1)$$

Figure 3: Mapping property of the deformation gradient \mathbf{F} . Due to the deformation process the initial fiber direction \mathbf{A} is transformed to direction \mathbf{a} in the deformed configuration.

Following objectivity, the free energy function Ψ is introduced as a function of the right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor \mathbf{C} and the structural tensor $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{A} \otimes \mathbf{A}$ containing information about the materials orientation (cf. Schroeder [19]). Carefully note, that the free energy function is invariant with regard to orthonormal transformations \mathbf{R} and therefore has to fulfill the condition (cf. Truesdell et al. [23], Lurie [10], Suhubi [20], Rivlin et al. [18])

$$\Psi(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{M}) = \Psi(\mathbf{R} * \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{R} * \mathbf{M}) \quad \forall \mathbf{R} \quad (2)$$

where the operator $*$ denotes the Rayleigh product. The extension of an isotropic St. Venant material according to Schroeder [19] provides the basis of the formulation of an initially transversely isotropic hyperelasticity constitutive law. The necessary shift to large deformation is obtained by substituting the linear deformation representation $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ by the Green strain

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{G}) \quad (3)$$

with \mathbf{G} is the metric tensor in an *Lagrangian* setting. The free energy function used throughout this work can be divided into isotropic and anisotropic contributions

$$\Psi = \Psi_{iso}(\mathbf{C}) + \Psi_{aniso}(\mathbf{C}) \quad (4)$$

in terms of

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{iso} &= \frac{1}{8} (\text{tr}\mathbf{C} - 3)^2 + \frac{1}{4} \mu_T (\text{tr}\mathbf{C}^2 - 2\text{tr}\mathbf{C} + 3) \\ \Psi_{aniso} &= \frac{1}{4} \alpha (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A} - 1) (\text{tr}\mathbf{C} - 1) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{8} \beta (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A} - 1)^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (\mu_L - \mu_T) (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{C}^2\mathbf{A} - 2\mathbf{A}\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A} + 1). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Hereby, λ , μ_T , μ_L , α and β are independent material parameters describing transversal isotropy.

Following standard arguments, the second Piola-Kirchhoff stresses can be identified as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{S} &= 2 \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{M})}{\partial \mathbf{C}} \\
 &= \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{M})}{\partial \mathbf{E}} \\
 &= \frac{\partial \Psi_{iso}(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{M})}{\partial \mathbf{E}} + \frac{\partial \Psi_{aniso}(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{M})}{\partial \mathbf{E}} \\
 &= \mathbf{S}_{iso} + \mathbf{S}_{aniso}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Further differentiation with respect to the deformation measure gives the moduli

$$\mathbb{C}^t = 4 \partial_{\mathbf{C}}^2 \Psi. \tag{7}$$

This formulation yields a structure known from Hooke's law at small deformations

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbb{C}^0 : \mathbf{E} \tag{8}$$

where \mathbb{C}^0 depicts the standard representation of a pristine transversely isotropic stiffness tensor. Regarding an implementation into Abaqus, the stresses and according moduli in the Eulerian configuration are obtained by standard push-forward operations.

2.2 Three-dimensional damage criterion for unidirectional fiber reinforced thermoplastics

One of the major issues for modeling the onset and propagation of damage in fiber reinforced plastics, is the setting up of a computational material model that captures the materials microstructural behavior in a realistic way. Extensive investigations on the failure behavior of unidirectional reinforced composites (Puck [17], Hinton et al. [9], Camanho et al. [2,3], Maimí et al. [12] and many others) indicate, that failure occurs in different forms and sizes that strongly depend on the loading conditions. The main task of a realistic computational model for such behavior is to establish, if, when and how damage occurs and to give a sound prediction how the material behavior changes with further damage evolution.

Figure 4: Depiction of the action plane coordinate system $\{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{x}_t\}$ with respect to material system $\{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3\}$ with its active tension components σ_n, τ_{nt} and τ_{n1} (cf. Puck [17]). The orientation of the action plane can be identified by the angle θ between the coordinate base $\mathbf{x}_2 = \mathbf{e}_2$ and the normal of the action plane $\mathbf{x}_n = \bar{\mathbf{e}}_n$ by rotation around \mathbf{x}_1 which corresponds to the fiber direction.

In the work presented here, four different failure modes are considered: *tensile inter-fiber failure* (IFF^+), *compressive inter-fiber failure* (IFF^-), both appearing on the transversal plane, *tensile fiber failure* (FF^+), and *compressive fiber failure* (FF^-). Their manifestation can be predicted for any given three-dimensional loading case. A combination of the three-dimensional failure criteria by Puck [17] and the LaRC04 criterion (cf. Pinho [16]), modified according to Maimí et al. [12], has been implemented. In order to distinguish whether a certain loading scenario leads to failure, the stress-dependent scalar *effort value* ε_i is introduced, where $i \in \{IFF^+, IFF^-, FF^+, FF^-\}$ represents the different failure modes. Carefully note that Puck's action plane concept was applied here. This yields the angle Θ for which the probability of failure in that transversal plane is at its maximum under a given stress state (cf. Figure 4). The criteria used are summarized in Table 1.

Failure mode	Criterion	Condition
FF^+	$\varepsilon_{FF^+} = \frac{S_{11}}{X_T}$	$S_{11} > 0$
FF^-	$\varepsilon_{FF^-} = \frac{S_{11}}{X_C}$	$S_{11} < 0$
IFF^+	$\varepsilon_{IFF^+} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{R_{\perp}^+} - \frac{p_{\perp\Psi}^+}{R_{\perp\Psi}^A}\right)^2 S_{nn}^2 + \left(\frac{S_{nt}}{R_{\perp\perp}^A}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{S_{n1}}{R_{\perp\parallel}}\right)^2 + \frac{p_{\perp\Psi}^+}{R_{\perp\Psi}^A} S_{nn}}$	$S_{nn} > 0$
IFF^-	$\varepsilon_{IFF^-} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{p_{\perp\Psi}^-}{R_{\perp\Psi}^A}\right)^2 S_{nn}^2 + \left(\frac{S_{nt}}{R_{\perp\perp}^A}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{S_{n1}}{R_{\perp\parallel}}\right)^2 + \frac{p_{\perp\Psi}^-}{R_{\perp\Psi}^A} S_{nn}}$	$S_{nn} < 0$

Table 1: Implemented effort functions to characterize fiber and inter-fiber failure. In the present model four different failure mechanisms are considered: Fiber failure due to tensile and compressive load, ε_{FF^+} and ε_{FF^-} (cf. Maimí et al. [12], Deuschle [6]), and inter-fiber failure due to tensile and compressive load, ε_{IFF^+} and ε_{IFF^-} (cf. Puck [17] for further information)

2.3 Damage evolution laws and calculation of damaged stresses

In order to model damage initiation, the *damage activation function* F_i is introduced. For the case

$$F_i(\varepsilon_i) = \varepsilon_i - 1 < 0 \quad (9)$$

purely elastic loading and no damage evolution will occur. Otherwise for if $F_i(\varepsilon_i) \geq 0$ a set of damage variables \bar{d}_i are calculated as a function of the effort value ε_i , operating on the action plane Θ

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{d}_i &= \bar{d}_i(\varepsilon_i(\Theta)) \\ &= 1 - \frac{1}{\varepsilon_i} \exp(A_i(1 - \varepsilon_i)). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

A reduction of mesh sensitivity during damage localization is obtained by application of the crack band model according to Bažant [1]. Therefore, the *adjustment parameters* A_i are calculated in such a manner that the equation for dissipated energy density under an uniaxial test

$$g_i = \int_0^\infty \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \bar{d}_i} \dot{\bar{d}}_i dt = \int_1^\infty \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \bar{d}_i} \frac{\partial \bar{d}_i}{\partial \varepsilon_i} d\varepsilon_i = \frac{G_i}{l^*} \quad (11)$$

is fulfilled at all times. Hereby l^* is the characteristic length for the respective finite element and G_i is the fracture toughness for the associated loading case. The numerical implementation is described in further detail in Maimí et al. [11]. In literature, several ways of tensorial damage representations are suggested, such as vector-valued, second- or higher order descriptions. For this work and following Murakami et al. [15], Cordebois et al. [5] and Murakami [14], a symmetric second-order damage tensor

\mathbf{D} is chosen, that varies between zero at the beginning and unity at the fully damaged state. Taking into account the damage variables \bar{d}_i calculated on the action plane, the trial damage tensor \mathbf{D}^* reads

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}^* &= D_{ij}^* \bar{\mathbf{e}}_i \otimes \bar{\mathbf{e}}_j \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \bar{d}_1^* & 0 & 0 \\ & \bar{d}_n^* & 0 \\ \text{sym} & & 0 \end{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{e}}_i \otimes \bar{\mathbf{e}}_j. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

This damage tensor is then compared to the damage tensor \mathbf{D}^n induced during the load history. In order to obtain thermodynamic consistency ($\dot{\mathbf{D}} > 0$), the damage update has the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D} &\leftarrow \mathbf{D}^n + \Delta \mathbf{D} \\ &= \mathbf{D}^n + \begin{pmatrix} \langle \bar{d}_1^* - \bar{d}_1^n \rangle_+ & 0 & 0 \\ & \langle \bar{d}_n^* - \bar{d}_n^n \rangle_+ & 0 \\ \text{sym} & & 0 \end{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{e}}_i \otimes \bar{\mathbf{e}}_j \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \bar{d}_1 & 0 & 0 \\ & \bar{d}_n & \bar{d}_{nt}^n \\ \text{sym} & & \bar{d}_t^n \end{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{e}}_i \otimes \bar{\mathbf{e}}_j \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where the operator $\langle \cdot \rangle_+$ denotes the positive Macaulay brackets. $\Delta \mathbf{D}$ does not only contain information about the magnitude of damage growth, but also the directionality of damage evolution. Therefore, \mathbf{D} describes the change of symmetry class and increasing anisotropy. The damaged stiffness tensor on the action plane Θ , \mathbb{C}^Θ is obtained using the *energy equivalence* approach of Carol [4]

$$\mathbb{C}^\Theta(\mathbf{D}) = \mathbb{B}(\mathbf{D}) : \mathbb{C}^0 : \mathbb{B}(\mathbf{D})^T \quad (14)$$

with $\mathbb{C}^\Theta = \mathbb{C}^0$ for $\hat{\mathbf{D}} = 0$, where \mathbb{C}^Θ denotes the damaged stiffness tensor on the inclined action plane and $\mathbb{B}(\hat{\mathbf{D}})$ describes the 4th order *active damage effect* tensor as a function of damage state $\hat{\mathbf{D}}(d_i)$, defined on the principal system of the damage. Carefully note, that due to multiplication of the damage effect tensor $\mathbb{B}(\hat{\mathbf{D}})$ with the stiffness tensor \mathbb{C}^0 in Equation 14 from both sides, major symmetry of secant stiffness and compliance is preserved. Back-transformation yields the damaged stiffness tensor in the material system

$$\mathbb{C} = \mathbf{R}^T(\Theta) * \mathbb{C}^\Theta. \quad (15)$$

Finally, the damaged stresses can be written according to

$$\mathbf{S}^d = \mathbb{C} : \mathbf{E}. \quad (16)$$

3 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The proposed model was implemented into the commercial finite element code Abaqus using the implicit user material subroutine UMAT. The capability of taking into account both the tension/compression anisotropy in damage evolution and the resulting damage effects with respect to different loading directions is demonstrated in the following by means of two numerical use cases involving single element simulation for a fictitious material.

3.1 Tensile loading-unloading scenario

As a first example, a tensile transverse loading in 2-direction and a subsequent unloading scenario is investigated. A transverse loading cycle is shown in Figure 5. Figure 5a shows the stress-strain relation, whereas Figure 5b depicts the evolution of the damage variable that is associated to the loading direction. It can be seen that the proposed model predicts damage onset in loading direction without any previous

inelastic material behavior (O-A). Exceeding the transverse tensile stiffness X_T , stiffness degradation follows due to damage evolution (A-B). Carefully note that only the damage variable d_2 along the loading direction grows. The perpendicular damage variable d_3 stays zero. This behavior changes the symmetry class of the stiffness tensor from transversely isotropic to orthotropic. During unloading, the degraded stiffness becomes visible by a reduced secant (B-O). However, the calculated damage variables stay constant (cf. Figure 5b), which is a requirement for thermodynamic correctness.

Figure 5a: Stress-strain curve for an uniaxial tension test (O-A-B) and unloading (B-O) in 2-direction.

Figure 5b: Damage evolution in 2-direction during uniaxial tensile test with subsequent unloading.

3.2 Compressive loading-unloading scenario

The second example examines the model response under compressive load reversal. The loading cycle under compression is depicted in Figure 6. Again, Figure 6a shows the stress-strain relationship, while Figure 6b monitors the evolution of damage.

At first, the material does not see any degradation of stiffness (O-A). As soon as the tension reaches the material strength for compression X_C (at A), damage grows (O-B). In contrast to the first example, damage evolves now not only in the direction of external load, but, due to the inclination of the damage system by Θ , also in perpendicular direction. The underlying model representation yields that the crack emerging due to external load is visible throughout the transverse isotropic plane. Note, that damage evolution in the various directions is highly dependent on the occurring orientation of the crack system. Once more, the evolution of damage changes the symmetry class of the stiffness tensor. During unloading (B-O) the calculated damage state remains unchanged.

Figure 6a: Stress-strain curve for an uniaxial compression test (O-A-B) and unloading (B-O) in 2-direction.

Figure 6b: Display of damage evolution in 2- and 3-direction during uniaxial tensile test with subsequent unloading.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, a three-dimensional constitutive model for the prediction of the onset and growth of damage in unidirectional reinforced plastics was introduced. Due to the application of this model in meso-models of weave-reinforced RVEs, which are objected to large deformation (especially rotation), a large strain formulation to describe deformation was suggested. The material response and failure criteria are evaluated with the help of entities defined in the *Lagrangian setting*. During damage evolution, it is ensured that the computed dissipated energy is independent of geometric discretization, yielding objective numerical solutions with respect to discretization when applied in the finite element analysis of more complex structures. The model was implemented in an implicit material subroutine UMAT for the finite element code Abaqus. Two representative numerical use cases were presented using a fictitious material. It could be shown that the predicted kinematics of damage evolution is in a good agreement with the expected material behavior. Current work focusses on extending the proposed model towards an accurate prediction of material response under subsequent loading and unloading scenarios, including the influence of tension/compression anisotropy on active and passive damage effects.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. P. Bažant and B. H. Oh. Crack band theory for fracture of concrete. *Matériaux et Constructions*, 16(3): 155–177, May 1983.
- [2] P. P. Camanho. Mechanical response of composites. Number 10 in *Computational methods in applied sciences*. Springer, Dordrecht, 2008.
- [3] P. P. Camanho, A. Arteiro, A. R. Melro, G. Catalanotti, and M. Vogler. Three-dimensional invariant-based failure criteria for fibereinforced composites. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 55:92–107, March 2015.
- [4] I. Carol, E. Rizzi, and K. Willam. On the formulation of anisotropic elastic degradation. {I}. Theory based on a pseudo-logarithmic damage tensor rate. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 38(4):491–518, January 2001.
- [5] J. P. Cordebois and F. Sidoroff. Endommagement anisotrope en élasticité et plasticité. *JMTA*, Numéro spécial, pages 45–60, 1982.
- [6] H. M. Deuschle. 3D failure analysis of UD fibre reinforced composites Puck's theory within FEA. *Inst. für Statik und Dynamik der Luft- und Raumfahrtkonstruktionen*, Stuttgart, 2010.
- [7] J. Fish. *Practical multiscaling*. John Wiley & Sons, 2013.
- [8] J. M. Guedes and N. Kikuchi. Preprocessing and postprocessing for materials based on the homogenization method with adaptive finite element methods. *Computer methods in applied mechanics and engineering*, 83(2): 143–198, 1990.
- [9] M. J. Hinton, A. S. Kaddour, and P. D. Soden. *Failure criteria in fibre reinforced polymer composites: the world-wide failure exercise*. Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2004.
- [10] A. I. Lurie. *Nonlinear theory of elasticity*. Number 36 in *North-Holland series in Applied Mathematics and Mechanics*. North-Holland, Elsevier Science Pub. Co, Amsterdam, New York, 1990.
- [11] P. Maimí, P. P. Camanho, J. A. Mayugo, and C. G. Dávila. A continuum damage model for composite laminates: Part II – Computational implementation and validation. *Mechanics of Materials*, 39(10): 909–919, October 2007.
- [12] P. Maimi, J. A. Mayugo, and P. P. Camanho. A three-dimensional damage model for transversely isotropic composite laminates. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 42(25): 2717–2745, September 2008.
- [13] C. Miehe and A. Koch. Computational micro-to-macro transitions of discretized microstructures undergoing small strains. *Archive of Applied Mechanics*, 72(4): 300–317, 2002.
- [14] S Murakami. Anisotropic damage theory and its application to creep crack growth analysis. *Constitutive Laws for Engineering Materials: Theory and Applications.*, 1: 187–194, 1987.

- [15] S. Murakami and N. Ohno. A Continuum Theory of Creep and Creep Damage. In A. R. S. Ponter and D. R. Hayhurst, editors, *Creep in Structures: 3rd Symposium*, Leicester, UK, September 8–12, 1980, pages 422–444. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1981.
- [16] S. T. Pinho, C. G. Dávila, P. P. Camanho, L. Iannucci, and P. Robinson. Failure models and criteria for FRP under in-plane or three-dimensional stress states including shear non-linearity. 2005.
- [17] A. Puck. *Festigkeitsanalyse von Faser-Matrix-Laminaten: Modelle für die Praxis*. Hanser, München, 1996.
- [18] R. S. Rivlin and J. L. Ericksen. Stress-Deformation Relations for Isotropic Materials. In *Collected Papers of R.S. Rivlin: Volume I and II*, pages 911–1013. Springer New York, New York, 1997.
- [19] J. Schröder. Theoretische und algorithmische Konzepte zur phänomenologischen Beschreibung anisotropen Materialverhaltens. PhD thesis, Institut für Mechanik und numerische Mechanik, Universität Hannover, Hannover, 1996.
- [20] E. S. Suhubi. *Thermoelastic solids in continuum physics*. In *Thermoelastic solids in continuum physics*. New York, 1975.
- [21] P. M. Suquet. Local and global aspects in the mathematical theory of plasticity. *Plasticity Today: Modelling, Methods and Applications*, Elsevier: 279–309, 1985.
- [22] K. Terada and N. Kikuchi. A class of general algorithms for multi-scale analyses of heterogeneous media. *Computer methods in applied mechanics and engineering*, 190(40): 5427–5464, 2001.
- [23] C. Truesdell and W. Noll. *The non-linear field theories of mechanics*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2004.